

CODING SCHEME for

(1) sampling judgments/cases

(2) extracting basic information on court hearings

(3) extracting basic information on offence/trial/sentence

(4) extracting basic information on Appeal

(1) SAMPLING JUDGMENTS/CASES	
Keywords found in case used for sampling
(2) EXTRACTING BASIC INFORMATION ON COURT HEARINGS (code as 99 if not stated and cannot be inferred)	
Neutral Citation Number (including year)	Alphanumeric
Case Number	Numeric
Date of Appeal Court Judgment	Numeric
Appeal Court Judges Names	Text
Case Name (e.g., Regina v. Casim Scott)	Text
Offender Representative Name	Text
Crown/Attorney General Representative Name	Text
(3) EXTRACTING BASIC INFORMATION ON OFFENCE/TRIAL/SENTENCE (code as 99 if not stated and cannot be inferred; if more than one offender/victim then differentiate by using surname)	
ConvCourtName(s) Court Name(s) where Offender Convicted/Pled Guilty	Text (List all courts if convicted/pled guilty at MORE than one court)
ConvictPleaDate Conviction/Guilty Plea Date(s)	Numeric (List all)
ConvictOffence What Offence(s) was Offender Convicted of?	Text (List all)
AcquitOffence What Offence(s) was Offender Acquitted of?	N/A OR Text (List all)
Did Offender Confess/Plead Guilty? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If YES, at what point during proceedings? PleaPoint 	Yes/No <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If YES, in police presence/at first court appearance/in court after first appearance but before trial/in court at first day of trial/in court after first day of trial/Don't know
What was the RemandDecision for Offender? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If REMANDED in CUSTODY, duration? RemandCustodyTime 	Unconditional Bail/Conditional Bail/ Remanded into custody/Don't know <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If REMANDED in CUSTODY, list how long/Don't know
SentCourtName Court Name where Offender Sentenced	Text
Sentence(s) Received	Text (List sentence for each offence)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If MORE than one sentence, then how are they to be served? SentServe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If MORE than one sentence, are they all concurrent/all consecutive/combination of consecutive and concurrent/Don't know
WhatAncilliary What ancillary orders were applied?	Select all that apply E.G. Criminal behaviour orders/Compensation orders/Confiscation orders/Deprivation orders/Disqualification from driving/Drink banning orders/Disqualification from being a company director/Financial reporting order/Football banning orders/Forfeiture orders/Parenting orders/Restitution orders/Restraining orders/Serious crime prevention order/Sexual harm prevention orders/Other/Don't know
OffSex Offender(s) Gender	All Male/All Female/Male&Female
OffAgeOffence Offenders(s) Age at Time of Offence	Numeric/Don't know
OffJobOffence Offender(s) Employment Status at Time of Offence	Employed/Self-employed/Unemployed/Student/Retired/Other/Don't know
OffHomeOffence Offender(s) Accommodation Status at Time of Offence	Had fixed address/Homeless/Temporary accommodation/Don't know
OffMentalOffence Offender(s) Mental Health at Time of Offence	Had mental health problems/Has learning difficulties/Other/Don't know
OffIntoxOffence Was Offender Intoxicated at Time of Offence?	Yes-drinking/Yes-drugs/Yes-drinking&drugs/No/Don't know
OffVicRelation Offender-Victim Relationship	Stranger/Relative/Acquaintance/Don't know
VictimType	Individual person/Organisation
VicNum Number of Victims	Numeric
VicSex Victim(s) Gender	All Male/All Female/Male&Female
VicAgeOffence Victim(s) Age at Time of Offence	Numeric
VicJobOffence Victim(s) Employment Status at Time of Offence	Employed/Self-employed/Unemployed/Student/Retired/Other/Don't know
VicHomeOffence Victim(s) Accommodation Status at Time of Offence	Had fixed address/Homeless/Temporary accommodation/Don't know
VicMentalOffence Victim(s) Mental Health at Time of Offence	Had mental health problems/Has learning difficulties/Other/Don't know
VicIntoxOffence Was Victim Intoxicated at Time of Offence?	Yes-drinking/Yes-drugs/Yes-drinking&drugs/No/Don't know
ProsEvidTypeTrial Which Types of Evidence Did <u>Prosecution</u> Present at Trial?	Select all that apply E.G. CCTV, Victim testimony, Identification line-up, Eye-witness testimony, Police testimony, Expert report/testimony, Cross-admissibility of counts, Victim is credible, Offender has bad character, Fingerprint match, Testimony of co-accused, Offender took victim property, Submission of 'no case to answer', DNA match, Digital

	forensic evidence, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]
DefEvidTypeTrial Which Types of Evidence Did <u>Defence</u> Present at Trial?	<u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Offender denies offence, Offender claims to have alibi, No clothing found matching offender's, No recovery of stolen goods from offender, Previous ruling in another court case, Consistency of offender evidence in court and at police interview, Offender of previous good character, Lack of DNA evidence to support allegations, Lack of medical evidence to support allegations, Victim is not credible/is unreliable, Question admissibility of some item of evidence, Offender admits only to lesser offence, Offender states co-accused is responsible for main offence, Offender argues he/she left scene before main offence committed, Offender uses bad character evidence against co-accused, 'Cut-throat' defence, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]
PreSentReport What was the Pre-sentence Report Assessment Presented to Sentencing Court?	Low/Medium/High risk of <u>reoffending</u> /Don't know
AggFactSent What Aggravating Factors did Court Mention When Sentencing Offender?	<u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Offence committed whilst on bail for other offences, Failure to respond to previous sentences, Offence motivated by, or demonstrating, hostility based on the victim's disability (or presumed disability), Previous conviction(s), particularly where a pattern of repeat offending is disclosed, Planning of an offence, An intention to commit more serious harm than actually resulted from the offence, Offenders operating in groups or gangs, 'Professional' offending, Commission of the offence for financial gain (where this is not inherent in the offence itself), High level of profit from the offence, An attempt to conceal or dispose of evidence, Failure to respond to warnings or concerns expressed by others about the offender's behavior, Offence committed whilst on licence, Offence motivated by hostility towards a minority group, or a member or members of it, Deliberate targeting of vulnerable victim(s), Commission of an offence while under the influence of alcohol or drugs, Use of a weapon to frighten or injure victim, Deliberate and gratuitous violence or damage to property, over and above what is needed to carry out the offence, Abuse of power, Abuse of a position of trust, Multiple victims, An especially serious physical or psychological effect on the victim, even if unintended, Location of the offence (for example, in an isolated place), Offence is committed against those working in the public sector or

	<p>providing a service to the public, Presence of others for example, relatives, especially children or partner of the victim, Additional degradation of the victim (for example, taking photographs of a victim as part of a sexual offence), In property offences-high value (including sentimental value) of property to the victim, or substantial consequential loss (for example, where the theft of equipment causes serious disruption to a victim's life or business), [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>MitFactSent What Mitigating Factors did Court Mention When Sentencing Offender?</p>	<p><u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> A greater degree of provocation than normally expected, mental illness or disability, Offender showed genuine remorse, Offender made admissions to police in interview, Offender was of previous good character/offence out of character, Offender has no (relevant) previous convictions, Offender voluntarily sought therapy/counselling, Offender voluntarily quit alcohol/determined to address alcohol addiction, Offender voluntarily quit drugs/determined to address drug addiction, Offender has serious medical condition, Offender has mental disorder/learning disability (not linked to commission of offence), Offender experienced 'bad patch' in life during time of offence, Offender age/lack of maturity affecting responsibility, Offender sole/primary carer for dependant relatives, Lapse of time/long delay before prosecution not fault of offender, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>VicImpactStatement Was Victim Impact Statement Given at Original Sentencing?</p>	<p>Yes/No/Don't know</p>
<p>(4) EXTRACTING BASIC INFORMATION ON APPEAL (code as 99 if not stated and cannot be inferred; if more than one offender/victim then differentiate by using surname)</p>	
<p>Who is Appellant?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If Offender is Appellant, Were There any Co-defendants/co-accused in Case? If YES, how many? CoDefAccNum 	<p>Offender/Attorney General/Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> N/A/Yes/No <p>If YES, numeric</p>
<p>AppealAgainst</p>	<p>Conviction is unsafe/Sentence is unduly excessive/Sentence is unduly lenient/Both conviction is unsafe & sentence is unduly excessive/Other e.g., application for extension of time to appeal</p>
<p>AppealGround Ground(s) for Appeal</p>	<p><u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Trial judge did not admit evidence undermining witness credibility, Trial judge did not properly/fully sum up the case, Trial judge gave own views on evidence/case that might bias jury, Trial judge admitted evidence which was prejudicial, Trial judge should have discharged jury</p>

	<p>after being exposed to prejudicial evidence, Sentencing judge should have put offence in a lower category of seriousness, Sentencing judge should have put offence in a higher category of seriousness, Sentence is 'excessive', Offender had practical difficulties in obtaining legal representation/legal documentation for making an appeal within the allotted timeframe, Exercise of judicial discretion was 'Wednesbury' unreasonable, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>Which Sentencing Guideline/Law/Act etc does Appeal Court Mention? SentGuideWhich</p>	<p>List</p>
<p>AppealOutcome Outcome of Appeal</p>	<p>Dismissed-Failed-Refused/Allowed&Conviction Quashed-Unsafe/Allowed&Sentence Replaced by More Excessive Sentence/Allowed&Sentence Replaced by More Lenient Sentence/Mixed Decision e.g., Conviction Allowed but Sentence Changed [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>ReasonQuashConv Appeal Court Basis Given for Why Conviction is Unsafe-Quashed</p>	<p><u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Appeal court believes trial judge asked jury to perform task that was too difficult for them or they might not perform reliably, Appeal court believes jury was inappropriately told of defendants' previous convictions, Appeal court believes jury could not be sure that defendant was same person as in CCTV/photo, Appeal court believes police did not use best practice, Appeal court believes trial judge should not have admitted some evidence, Appeal court believes jury was not given sufficient guidance by trial judge, Appeal court believes it was inappropriate for jury not to be allowed to see some evidence, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>ReasonSentExcessNotLenient Appeal Court Basis Given for Why Sentence is Unduly Excessive/Not Lenient</p>	<p><u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Appeal court believes offender has strong personal mitigation, Appeal court believes offender has realistic prospect of rehabilitation, Appeal court believes offender does not have history of poor compliance with court orders, Appeal court believes offender does not pose significant continuing risk to public, Appeal court believes sentencing judge did not refer to relevant sentencing guideline, Appeal court believes sentencing judge did not have a real option to pass anything other than a custodial sentence, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>
<p>ReasonSentLenientNotExcess Appeal Court Basis Given for Why Sentence is Unduly Lenient/Not Excessive</p>	<p><u>Select all that apply E.G.</u> Appeal court believes sentencing judge did not refer to relevant sentencing guideline, Appeal court believes sentencing judge did not have a real option to pass anything other than a custodial sentence, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]</p>

ReasonDismiss Appeal Court Basis Given for
Why Appeal Dismissed-Failed-Refused

Select all that apply E.G. Trial/sentencing judge considered all relevant facts in appropriate way and came to correct conclusion/decision, Trial/sentencing judge approach and decision cannot be faulted, Offender had knew there was no ground for appeal, Offender let too much time pass before appealing, Appeal court is not persuaded by submissions on behalf of appellant, Appellant also used a 'cut-throat' defence, Trial judge made correct judgement regarding admissibility of some evidence, Trial judge made correct decision regarding inadmissibility of some evidence, No criticism is made by appellant regarding trial judges' direction/instruction to jury, Appeal court believes jury will follow/obey trial judges' directions/instructions, Trial judge's summing up was not the sole thing the jury relied on, Appeal court believes jury understood the issues in the case, The original sentence fell within the guidelines range, Appeal has no merit, [ADD ANY OTHER NOT LISTED HERE]